

EFFECT OF THICKNESS ON IMPACT DAMAGE AND CAI BEHAVIOR

Y. Aoki¹, H. Samejima², H. Suemasu² and Y. Nagao¹

1: Advanced Composite Group, Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency,
6-13-1 Osawa, Mitaka-shi, Tokyo 181-0015, Japan
aoki.yuichiro@jaxa.jp

2: Department of Mechanical Engineering, Sophia University
7-1 Kioicho, Chiyoda-ku, Tokyo 102-8554, Japan
suemasu@sophia.ac.jp

SUMMARY

This study investigated the effect of thickness on impact-induced damage and compression-after-impact (CAI) characteristics of conventional aerospace-grade CFRP laminates. Impact and CAI tests were conducted on quasi-isotropic laminates with four different thicknesses (16 ply, 24 ply, 32 ply, 64 ply) with reference to ASTM 7136/D and 7137D. Impacts with several energies were applied to specimens to examine the effect of thickness on impact response, delamination area and size, and residual compressive strength. It was found that delamination size and shape depend on specimen thickness, even with the same impact energy. The impact energy normalized by the thickness produced different delamination characteristics, depending on the stiffness of the laminate. A deeper understanding of the effect of specimen thickness on impact response and CAI strength is important.

Keywords: Delamination, Low velocity Impact, CAI strength, Thickness effect, CFRP laminate

1. INTRODUCTION

Compression-after-impact (CAI) tests are considered to be a crucial evaluation in the design process of composite primary structures. Design allowable strain limits of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) are mainly defined from CAI or OHC results for composite primary structures, and these limit values govern weight reduction ratios. CAI tests are also considered to be a material screening device for evaluating new composite systems for structural applications. Although CAI testing does not seem to be optimal for this purpose, thousands of CAI tests have been conducted by companies that are suppliers of advanced composite materials. Therefore, CAI tests are important in both the aircraft and composite material industries, and a deep understanding of the mechanics of CAI tests is indispensable when evaluating the test results.

However, ambiguity in the mechanics of CAI failure behavior may lead to misunderstanding of test data and send material development researchers in the wrong direction. In order to clarify the mechanism of CAI behavior, many researchers began mainly experimental investigations more than a decade ago [e.g. 1-7]. Their findings

fall into two groups corresponding to two experimental steps: impact-related and compression-related. Other researchers worked with numerical analysis. [e.g. 8-13].

Some researchers focused on the effects of specimen size, thickness or stacking sequence on the mechanical behavior and strength of CFRP laminates [14-17], reporting that specimen thickness significantly affects CFRP behavior and strength, especially in compressive tests.

The purpose of this study was to investigate the effect of specimen thickness on CAI behavior and strength using a conventional CAI test standard. An approximate scenario [tracing the path] from impact-induced damage to subsequent compressive failure and residual strength will be identified.

2. PREPARATION OF SPECIMENS

Specimens were fabricated from unidirectional carbon fiber prepreg (Q-C133): an intermediate modulus-high strength PAN-based carbon fiber (IM600) and 180°C cure-type toughened epoxy resin system (#133). The material system was supplied by TOHO TENAX Co., Ltd. (Japan). This material is widely used for aircraft structures because of its high resistance to CAI. A large amount of fundamental data for this material can be obtained from the internet website of JAXA-ACDB: <http://www.jaxa-acdb.com>. The stacking sequence of the CAI specimen was [45/0/-35/90]_ns with n = 2, 3, 4 and 8. The standard cure cycle recommended by TOHO TENAX Co., Ltd was used for fabrication of specimens using an autoclave system. The approximate fiber volume fraction was 55-58 %. Specimens were 150 mm long and 100 mm wide, cut from a parent panel in accordance with ASTM 7136/D. The nominal thickness and number of specimens with each lamination are shown in Table 1. All specimens were visually inspected before use.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Impact test and damage inspection

Impact was delivered to the specimen by a drop-weight with a hemispherical impactor of 15.9 mm (5/8 inch) diameter at room temperature (23°C±3°C). The impact test machine was an INSTRON 9250HV, with a rebound brake to prevent multiple impacts on the specimen by the impactor. The impact tests were conducted with different impact energies ranging from 1.7 to 13.4 J/mm, normalized by the thickness of the specimen. Impactor mass was 5.0 and 10 kg and the drop height was adjusted to provide an impact at the same energy level on specimens with different thicknesses. The impact velocity ranged from 1.43 to 4.06 m/sec. The specimens were clamped at four points by toggle rubbers shown as Fig. 1. Impact load, velocity and deflection of specimen were measured by an instrumented impactor (Dynatup). The energy absorbed by the specimen was calculated from the difference between the impactor's drop height and its rebound height after impact.

3.2 Damage inspection

After the impact test, the size and shape of the damage in the specimen were inspected by the phased array ultrasonic C-scan system (Toshiba Matrixeye 64 3D ultrasonic inspection system). The system has multiple transducers such that 64 channels of transducer and ultrasonic waves can be sent and received with multiple piezoelectric sensors. The system can obtain a three-dimensional ultrasonic image of the delamination inside the impacted specimen. Figure 2 shows an example of a three-dimensional ultrasonic image of the delamination in a 64 ply quasi-isotropic CFRP laminate after impact, as obtained by a 64 channel, 5 MHz linear array transducer in pulsed-echo mode. A three-dimensional delamination shape that looks like a spiral staircase can be seen extending from the top to the bottom surface. Dent depth and shape on the surface were also measured by depth gage with an accuracy of 0.01mm.

3.3 Compression test

The compression-after-impact test was carried out by a screw-driven testing machine, INSTRON 5589, under displacement control with a crosshead speed of 1.0 mm/min. The CAI test fixture described in the ASTM 7137D was used as shown in Fig. 3. Top and bottom edges were fixed and the edges were simply supported by knife edge fixtures. The compressive load, displacement and strains were measured by a KYOWA PCD-300 data logger with a sampling rate of 10 Hz during the test.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Impact behavior

The relationship between contact load and deflection during impact at impact energy of 6.7 J/mm is shown in Fig. 4. It was found that the initial stiffness depended on the specimen thickness. The load increased with deflection until it dropped off with damage growth above a certain load level. For 64 ply laminate, the load dropped significantly because of unstable damage growth. The load subsequently increased nonlinearly due to the large deflection with slight reduction of stiffness for other thin laminates. The unloading responses showed a crucial difference with the loading ones. In the impact test, the deflection was not measured but calculated from the integral of the impact velocity measured by the instrumented velocity detector, and this might have resulted in considerable error in traveling distance of the impactor, especially in the unloading process.

4.2 Impact-induced damage

The results of an ultrasonic scan from the top surface of the specimens impacted at a normalized energy of 6.7 J/mm are shown in Fig. 5. The shape of the entire delamination is clearly dependent on the thickness of the specimen, even at the same impact energy. The delamination size near the back surface tends to be larger than that near the top surface in all specimens. However, the delamination near the back surface

of 16 ply laminate tends to be larger in the fiber direction of the bottom layer, which is related closely to the bending crack in the bottom layer. The delamination shape became more circular for the thicker laminates. In the 64 ply laminate, the ultrasonic image shows comparatively large delaminations at the bottom surfaces, and an overall delamination region that was often hat-brim shaped.

Figure 6 shows the relationships between projected delamination area and normalized impact energy by thickness. Here, the projection area is defined as the envelope of the largest delamination radius and it should be noted that this projected area is not the total area of accumulated delaminations. Two important findings are implicitly described in Fig. 6: The existence of an impact energy delamination threshold of about 2 J/mm, and a proportional delamination area increase up to a certain impact energy level. However, in the thicker laminates, a hat-brim shaped delamination gave a comparatively large projection delamination area, therefore, there is a scattering of data at high energy levels. In addition, impactor penetration caused a saturation of the delamination area. This spread of delamination area will be an important factor when considering the optimum specimen size.

On the other hand, Fig. 7 shows the relationship between total delamination area and total impact energy. The total delamination area was calculated by accumulating the projection area of each delamination through the thickness, which can be calculated from each delamination radius obtained from detailed ultrasonic B and C scope images. This figure shows a very strong relationship between impact energy and delamination area. There is less scattering of data, which can be plotted as a straight line.

4.3 CAI strength

Figure 8 shows the relationship between total impact energy and CAI strength. In this figure, variation in CAI strength is clearly governed by the plate thickness in present method. That result is closely related to the final failure mode and compressive behavior of impacted CFRP laminates. In the CAI test, the boundary conditions employed were fixed at loading (top) and supporting (bottom) ends and simply supported at the side edges as specified in SACMA and ASTM testing methods. For the thin laminates, a buckling deformation tended to induce the propagation of delamination transverse to the loading direction at much smaller load level. The CAI strength of thinner laminates showed smaller CAI strength at the same impact energy. The thicker laminates tended to show a catastrophic failure when the delamination region extended across almost the entire width at the failure load.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The effect of thickness on the impact-induced damage and compression after impact (CAI) characteristics of conventional aerospace-grade CFRP laminates was investigated in this study. The main conclusions are as follows.

- The initial stiffness during impact depends on the specimen thickness. The load increased with deflection until it dropped at a certain load level due to damage growth. The load dropped significantly for the thick laminates because of unstable damage growth.
- The overall delamination shape became more circular and the entire delamination region tended to be hat-brim shaped in the thicker laminates.
- The total delamination area showed a clearer relationship with impact energy and delamination area than did the projected delamination area.
- The thinner laminates tended to have a lower CAI strength, which is closely related to the final failure mode and compressive behavior of impacted laminates.

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Table 1 Nominal thickness and number of specimens

Ply number	Nominal thickness	Stacking sequence	Number of specimens
16	2.3 mm	[45/0/-45/90] _{2s}	6
24	3.4 mm	[45/0/-45/90] _{3s}	6
32	4.7 mm	[45/0/-45/90] _{4s}	6
64	9.3 mm	[45/0/-45/90] _{8s}	6

(a) Overview

(b) Impact test fixture

Figure 1 Drop-weight impact testing machine.

Figure 2 Typical three-dimensional ultrasonic inspection result for the delamination of impacted 64 ply quasi-isotropic CFRP laminate: $[45/0/-45/90]_8s$

Figure 3 Test fixtures for compression-after-impact test.

Figure 4 Load-deflection curves from a 6.7 J/mm impact on laminates with different thicknesses.

Figure 5 Ultrasonic images of laminates of different thickness after a 6.7 J/mm impact.

Figure 6 Projected delamination area vs. normalized impact energy.

Figure 7 Total delamination area vs. total impact energy.

Figure 8 CAI strength vs. total impact energy.